

The Impact of Western Culture on the Transformation of Residential Patterns in One of The Heritage Areas In Baghdad (Neighborhood CREMAT / Salhiya - Baghdad Model)

Shatha A. Alamiri¹, Doaa M. Alzubaidy²

¹ D.Pro. University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

² A.L Alfarabi university college, Baghdad, Iraq

Keywords

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Abstract

The traditional housing of Baghdadi has undergone many transformations in the past century. This is noticed in many districts of traditional Baghdad and its heritage. In this period, architectural styles with Western influences were observed as a result of the political conditions and foreign colonization that swept the country. German architecture, English and French and other models in our old heritage stores, especially in the neighborhood of CREMAT in Salhia - Baghdad. With this level of complexity of the models, we have to disclose and study during the research process to reach the mechanisms and adaptation of Western models designed for an environment of a different nature adapted to our environment and the local Baghdad and take advantage of these global experiences in the design process. Therefore, the research highlighted the influence of Western culture on our Baghdadi architectural culture to preserve the landmarks of the past so that future children can see it. Ever since man's historical awareness of the past, the present and the future, he tried to record his present and preserve his past for the future. The urban heritage reflects the cultural identity of man: his past, his present and his future. Our Baghdad Municipality has been characterized by functional organization of the elements of the house, relying on the internal courtyard to provide the necessary privacy to the population and the use of local construction materials such as bricks, plaster, stone and palms and the use of the sheds in the internal atmosphere of the rooms. All examples of Baghdadi heritage architecture share a distinctive architectural character that belongs to the region and reflects all of its cultural, environmental and social conditions. Therefore, the research will try to reach the impact of these civilizations on the Baghdadi style, especially in the residential architecture of Baghdad. The objective of the research was to describe the effects of Western culture on the architectural style of the Salhia area and its adaptation to the local style of the region while attempting to come up with new and traditional indicators of transformation in residential patterns. In order to address the research problem, which is the phenomenon of divergence in the decisions of the traditional residential patterns in the locality of the CREMAT - Salhia, and to verify the goal of the desired research, the research plan is to analyze the chronological sequence of the ancient models in the region and identifying the identity of each model and then how to diagnose changes in traditional architectural styles through its holistic calendar and the appearance of the architectural style of the Salhia in this architectural form. The results showed the impact of Western cultures on the identity of the Baghdad residential area.

Introduction

The research was based on the analytical method of the architectural styles and methods of construction of the Baghdad residential units in Al-Kareemat district through the chronological sequence of these units and their impact on the design of the residential units. The study also adopted the method of transferring the field measurements that were taken for samples of the traditional and modern housing units into graphs and to demonstrate the influence of western culture on the Baghdadi architectural styles and explain the adaptation of western architecture to our local environment. With the diagnosis of patterns of Western architecture and its reflection on the domestic production of housing. The influence of the West in its attitudes and the nature of its products is unique and different from our own.

Figure , 1 / by researcher

2 PATTERNS IN HERITAGE AREAS OF BAGHDAD

2.1 The heritage areas of Baghdad and its history and the area of cremat especially

The Arab city with its traditional cohesive texture is the best example of the application of the concept of social interdependence at the city level as a whole, city planning and pathway processors in terms of width, height, direction and change of direction is the main stage of adaptation with the environment. Harmonized fabric can soften the effects of harsh climates and reduce their effects, especially high temperatures, solar radiation, dusty and warm winds, and thus reduce the total thermal load on the facades of buildings, especially residential units, where housing units constitute the largest proportion of total structural production in the Arab city. (1) The Karkh side of Baghdad, as we know it geographically, starts from the district of Al-Jaafir to the north and the Salhiya and the Krimat to the south and from the Tigris River east to the tombs of Sheikh Maarouf Al-Karkhi and Al-Junaid Al-Baghdadi. The Karkh area consists of several shops and a shop on a number of alleys. Each alley of a number of houses and shops most famous in Karkh (CREAMAT) is the river bordering the river because of the importance of water in particular in reference to the importance of water. This region is characterized by the beauty of the river and the coolness of the atmosphere in the summer.

2.2 The upgrowth of the cremation area and location

Al-Mahalla is located on the western side of Baghdad and its borders as stated in the Atlas of Baghdad, 1952 (Mahalat 218) adjacent to the Al-Ahraa Rasmi Bridge administratively the Salhiya area. The area was formerly large green farms and orchards, Maud and currently, Al-Ahrar Bridge. In July 1911, the German Maister Pasha arrived in Baghdad to take up his post as director of its works and opened his offices in Dar Kadhim Pasha (Turki origin) on the west bank of the Tigris River in the Krimat area. It is not just a winding alley from which there are short alleys that lead to the Tigris River and another to the center of the city. It is a popular place that has roots in the depths of

history and on its feet, it still has the secret of its existence. To the past, creams feel you are part of old Baghdad that you read about in the tales of the round city (As in Fig. 2,3). When you look at it, it takes time to reflect on its aesthetics, especially as the river, the boats and the movement of the land give it joy even though some of its old houses have become incapable of resisting nature. The most prominent of which is the British House of the British Embassy. This house is located in the southern part of Baghdad near the fence and not far from the proposed location of the railway station on the same bank to the south. On the morning of July 27, 1912 was an official celebration of the commencement of the development project in the presence of the governor Jamal Pasha and about 40 engineers, mostly Germans from the effects of the Baghdad Railway project that is located in the south-west of the city. (Garage Alawi and the role of rail in Salhia currently) was the compound in the era of construction is located outside the city limits so that the train comes out of the station and runs parallel to the western fence to the north towards Samarra. This was most prominent reason for the region's urban growth. The construction of this community contributed to the development of the Karkh side and its expansion in this direction in later years until it began to appear in later eras of modern important installations after it was limited to a number of residential shops and some shrines. Karkh witnessed developments in a series of important projects, including the development of the Baghdad Railway Station Iron, which became known as a station west of Baghdad and to the northwest of it, an airport was built (Muthanna airport currently) on a large land in 1931 considering that this site was then outside the city and far away from urbanization and the establishment of the Iraqi Radio House in 1936 took a position in Salhia near the Lord of Baghdad Station (3). Then the English came to do a bridge Mudd near the former Liberal camp soldiers Englishmen there. In the early 1920s, the railway complex and its neighbors, especially Salhia, became a large urban center in the 1920s and 1930s. There was a significant change in the urban style and lifestyle of the grove. The western influence was evident in the urban and architectural environment and the new residential neighborhoods such as the railway complex. Neighboring areas were based on straight and cross-border geometrical designs and if the new areas reflected a remarkable transformation and then a division of traditional folk architecture (As in Fig. 3), the first time to show the impact of these Western cultures on the local architecture in the creams.

Figure.3.morphological .creamat area by

Figure , 2, site by Google Earth

2.3 Nature of the fabric in the creams area:

The nature of the textile in the region began with the harmonious organic pattern developed by the needs of the population and the emergence of dilapidated buildings around which was the urban growth of the region and was the beginning of its emergence. Examples of this growth included the houses of the Ottoman rulers and the British Embassy where they are settled in the region in addition to the bridge Ahrar linking Karkh Rusafa and then railway station and housing railway workers and sites. The fabric of their work was transformed from an organic type to a straight-cut pattern that followed the developments in the area in Haifa Street and divided the area into two halves due to changes in the lifestyle of the people and their influence on the Western style as well as the British occupation of the area and the entry of cars during the same period, which forced the region to divide the streets geometrically to form an integrated road infrastructure (as in Figure, 4).

Figure.4, fabric area by researcher

3 .Factors Affecting The Origin And Development Of Traditional Residential Architecture

From the beginning of creation, the main concern of man was to try to adapt to his environment. Caves and huts were built in a primitive way during prehistoric times to protect against the danger of animals and aggressors and to overcome the various climatic fluctuations. Through his understanding, the phenomena of the environment and its geographical and climatic characteristics enable man to develop his habitat and in different ways benefiting from previous experiences in the development of construction methods and building materials to create a suitable residential environment. Residential architecture has been particularly affected by several factors including topography, climate, religious and social factors.

- Topography: Geography has an important role in the architectural configuration..
- Climate: Climate plays a major role in the emergence and development of residential buildings and in the formation and composition of the main building elements.
- Religious, social and cultural factors: The social environment has greatly influenced how residential buildings are created.
- Economic factors: Trade and agriculture are among the important activities that have contributed significantly to the development of traditional residential buildings. Libya has been one of the regions that served as a trade intermediary between Europe and Africa.
- Political and legislative factors: Political factors played an important role in the development of residential buildings in Libya. Islami, where people converted to Islam, the houses took another style in accordance with Islamic law. The houses were built in adjoining residential neighborhoods with inner courtyards, emphasizing privacy and respect for the neighbor. During the German and English occupation, T high-altitude multi-role balconies overlooking the wide openings on the outside and the current period is an extension of the period of openness to the outside and the full transfer of Western architecture that does not fit customs, traditions and climatic conditions prevailing.
- Building materials and technology.

4. The Chronological Sequence Of Patterns And Their Differences In The Area Of Creams And The Impact Of Western Culture On Their Residential Patterns

The style of architecture is characterized by its cohesive texture and its social and latent sustainability. It is unique in planning and design elements. Inclusion was not coincidental but rather a product of climatic, religious and social conditions. The spatial organization of the organic city is characterized by streets and twisted walks, and relatively large and open neighborhood and garden units and indoor gardens act as reservoirs of moderate cold air. The factors of economy and politics have had the greatest impact on the change of Baghdadi identity and style. This is noticed in the cremation area in Baghdad where Ottoman colonization began to occupy the area. The arrival of the Germans and the English was also influential as they left their design fingerprints on Baghdad. The difference between the Baghdad models was clear:

4.1 Traditional style Baghdadi in housing

- First: On the level of horizontal plans.
- Second: the level of sense of mass and space.
- Third: the level of the formation of façades.
- Fourth: The level of environmental and climatic treatments.

4.2 Western style in housing:

The Classical European style is characterized by the clarity of the values of form and art and we find the mass unit surrounded by a vast courtyard as an extension. This block stands alone and has clear features and express themselves strongly and simply and embody the features of nature around with the use of iron in the balconies and in the quarries. Additionally, there are statues in the entrances and massive columns were used to introduce the huge entrance. The German and English models are characterized by openness to the outside with balconies and chimneys and the presence of vertical windows. In addition, the use of iron in the facades with the high entrances to the level of the Earth and the decorations and inscriptions at the top of the building. Speaking of the influence of Western culture and its influence in the area of creams in Baghdad, at the beginning of the emergence of the region was the Ottoman governor controlled Baghdad where a palace was built. After that, the English came and built several houses in the region and then they moved to France to complete their studies and returned to the idea of the classic French style

of old Legg. In this period, the mid-fifties of the nineteenth century took over the Republic of Iraq; the government began a period of urban prosperity of Baghdad and tried to return the Baghdadi style in their homes. From here came the designs of House Zaher in response to the challenge of Western cultures to maintain the the old Baghdadi style. (Fig. 5,6) shows the difference of cultures and their impact on the model of the study area.

Figure,5,by researcher

Figure,6,by researcher

5 .What Is The Adaptation Of The Patterns Of The West With The Pattern Of Local Residential Environment In Baghdad

The planning of the traditional housing was fully compatible with the environment, with all its pros and cons, and it was achieved according to two strategies: protection and adaptation. Protection has been achieved by limiting the impact of the extreme natural environment conditions such as hot climate, relative humidity in some areas, elevation in other areas and the intensity of solar radiation. The adaptation was to exploit the potential of these harsh conditions and deal with them to achieve the thermal comfort of the inhabitants and the exploitation of natural energy sources such as the sun and wind. The use of the middle courtyard was one of the most important design principles in the architecture of different civilizations in Iraq despite the differences in the urban environments and in the urban environment. This is due to the ability of the building with a central courtyard to adapt to various conditions in terms of achieving a lot of environmental requirements, civilizational and aesthetic and social, such as privacy and protection from external hazards or harsh environment, especially in hot climates. We notice that the housing was initially designed in the middle courtyard of the original Baghdadi models open the spaces of the house and closed from the outside. This was clear on and off the Baghdadi style to achieve privacy and isolation from the outside and create an external environment integrated climate and socially interconnected at home as in (Figure 7). After the intervention of the political factor and the occupation of Baghdad by Western countries and the transfer of their cultures to us in the construction of buildings and houses in Baghdad, we note the mid-closing of the middle courtyard of the house from the top because their homes are not designed on the basis of the central courtyard. DONC entirely average in the design of Baghdadi houses and turned his job to the distributor spaces home and change its size and open large windows in the facades overlooking the outside and the construction of open balconies to the outside as in (Figure 8), all of these came Western Ktathirat on social traditions and patterns of architectural Baghdadi.

Figure,7,by researcher

Figure,8,by researcher

6. Indicators Of The New Transformations On The Traditional Residential Patterns In Baghdad

- At the planning level: the middle courtyard turned into a dynamic distributor or a transitional space in the house and shut it off from the top completely.

